

Current Problems in Teaching Physical Education

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Abstract: In the article, the fundamental reforms carried out in the field of physical education, the goals and objectives of public events in the fields of culture, medicine, education and sports, their content is the comprehensive maturity of young people studying for a profession, and their full response to the students of the time. such issues are covered.

The fundamental reforms carried out in our country, the goals and tasks of mass events in the fields of culture, medicine, education and sports, their content is the all-round maturity of young people who are studying for a profession, they fully respond to the students of the time, in which work to do, requires having all the qualities associated with feelings and beliefs of loyalty to the Motherland. The purpose of this is to emphasize that in the above "Physical Education" programs, there is full information about the study of national values in physical education classes, especially the ways of using national traditions in physical education, sports, travel, and national national games. no. This has a negative impact on the students' understanding of national traditions and the nature of physical education. Another aspect is that most physical education teachers cannot leave the program, creative approach and practical initiatives are rare. Such negative characteristics are manifested in the process of educational practices (pedagogical and organizational) of students.

It is known that physical education processes have their own characteristics. When analyzing the curriculum of the "Physical culture" educational direction, two directions are known, namely:

1. Students conduct training and skill improvement classes in the chosen sport specialty in the form, content and method common to all faculties in the republic and in the National Sports Institute.

2. Courses are organized on the competences of professors and teachers of the faculty, on special subjects of interest to them. These processes have a positive effect on students' acquisition of specialized concepts and knowledge at one or another level. However, it cannot be said that this situation is well established in all higher educational institutions, and their quality is at a high level. There are some objective and subjective reasons for this:

- educational manuals and recommendations embodying social and educational features of physical education and national traditions are not perfectly developed;
- the knowledge of traditions among teachers engaged in deepening theoretical concepts and practical-professional knowledge of sports is rather shallow;
- the topics of spiritual and physical maturity and their interrelationships are not covered in detail in abstracts, courses and graduation (diploma) works;
- in the I-II stages of physical culture education, little attention is paid to the content and essence of mass-cultural events held in sports facilities in the context of homework and independent work.

On the basis of the Resolution PQ-3031 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 3, 2017 "On measures for the further development of physical education and mass sports",

the selection of talented children, their practical tests and their mobilization to sports schools keyed. In such organizational, practical and educational conditions, sports performances and mass demonstrations used in national traditions can become important. For this reason, children's sports and national traditions are educational for students at all levels of physical culture faculties; it will be necessary to teach methods of proportionality from an organizational point of view. Such socio-educational teachings and practical activities should be taught during all theoretical and practical (sports) classes and sports training.

"Alpomish" and "Barchinoy", which belong to them, in the lessons and sports trainings held according to the type of sports in the curriculum (gymnastics, athletics, action games, wrestling, specialization, etc.) Tests have been symbolically continued from the life of our ancestors, reminding of traditional customs and traditions expressed in the content of national values. However, it is desirable to deeply inculcate relevant information about the epic "Alpomish" and other artistic works, historical, cultural and archaeological sources to students.

One of the most important activities is the formation of sufficient theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the training of physical education teachers, as in any field. According to the curriculum of the faculties of physical culture, it is prescribed to conduct a qualification practice (pedagogical and organizational training practice) within 18 weeks (6-8 semesters). In the first half of the III stage, physical education and extracurricular sports events, and practical assistance to teachers are expected to be observed. At the beginning of the second half of the IV stage, students conduct exemplary physical education classes, analyze the lessons of others, organize training in sports clubs, lead and referee public sports competitions.

Pedagogical observations, formal interviews with experienced teachers, students undergoing professional practice, scientific-theoretical analysis of the results of the dialogues led to the following comments:

- the responsible teachers of the theory and methodology of physical education, specialized departments of sports and pedagogy, psychology departments cooperate in conducting students' qualification practice;
- when preparing students for professional practice, guides (methodists) consistently study and monitor their interest in their profession, theoretical concepts and practical activities;
- at special meetings (conferences) organized to conduct professional practices, faculty heads, department heads introduce students to their main activities;
- school physical culture teachers, city (district) sports committees, employees of "Youth" sports association who participated in the conference (based on the proposal) are sharing experience with practical work;
- the heads of the schools are responsible for creating appropriate conditions and practical assistance in schools for conducting professional practices;
- students set an example by diligently studying the tasks set before them and putting their activities into practice.

In general, the cooperation of the school and the faculty is significantly manifested in the processes of preparation for professional practice and their implementation. However, there are serious shortcomings, deficiencies and some defects in the educational processes, especially in the professional practice of learning national traditions and their practical application.

These are:

1. The theoretical knowledge of students is lacking when conducting professional practice at a high level. Because, for one reason or another, practical experiences in conducting trainings, organizing competitions, getting students interested in them, and engaging them are not up to the level of demand.

2. The majority of students are good at organizational methods in physical education, physical

culture movement and sports it is shown that he is not learning, that he is not fully aware of sports news.

3. Lack of control by the faculty methodist, cases of not constantly analyzing the students' activities cause them to look coldly at their tasks.

4. School physical education teachers have deficiencies in providing practical assistance to their students-practitioners.

5. Students' creativity, collecting evidence related to course or graduation work, conducting research activities are at a low level.

6. The work of ensuring the active participation of students in public sports holidays and competitions is not well underway.

7. The use of traditions in the activities of school spirituality and enlightenment, youth social movement "Kamolot", "Yoshlik" physical education team council, class leaders and other official primary organizations in interaction with students is not at the level of demand.

Therefore, in the process of qualification practices, there are very few conversations and practical activities about the study of national values, the use of national traditions in the educational process, and their socio-educational features.

As a general conclusion, it should be said that the literature in the field of physical education and sports shows that the content of national traditions is not fully expressed in the events being held.

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